

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Yangi taraqqiyot davrida oliy ta'lim tizimining rivojlanish tendensiyalari	10
<i>Kirgizbayev Abdug'afvor Karimjonovich</i>	
Tebranma kimyoviy reaksiyalar mavzusini o'qitishning ahamiyati (Oksidlanish-qaytarilish reaksiyalari misolida).....	14
<i>Artiqov Maqsud Bahodirovich, Sultanov Miribek Jabbarbergenovich, Bazarbayeva Laylo Gulmirza qizi</i>	
Biologiya o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va metodlarning takomillashib borishi	17
<i>Azimov Ibragimjon Toshpulatovich, Toshpulatova Nigina Ibrohimjon qizi, Toshpulatova Maftuna Ibrohimjon qizi</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida bulutli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning didaktik imkoniyatlari.....	22
<i>Doniyorova Gulshan Toshmirzayevna</i>	
Tarbiya – insoniyat rivojlanishining ajralmas qismi	27
<i>Nayimova Aziza Dilmurot qizi</i>	
Bolalarga xos psixologik o'zgarishlar va ularning yechimlari.....	31
<i>Qodirova Malikaxon Kaxramonovna</i>	
Tibbiy ma'lumotlarni avtomatlashtirish: ma'lumotlarni to'plash, qayta ishlash va tahlil qilish uchun modulli vositalar.....	36
<i>Mamatov Maxtumquli Jumanazarovich, Rustamova Charosxon Rustamovna</i>	
Lexicon Changes in the 21st Century Royal English.....	39
<i>Sapayeva Yakutjan Maxmudovna</i>	
Bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilari uchun ritmik gimnastika darslarini tuzilishi	45
<i>Shaxbazova Gulrux Orifjon qizi, Xalilova Barnogul Abdulazizovna</i>	
Maktabgacha 6–7 yoshli bolalarda bilish kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda multimedaning o'rni	49
<i>Suvanova Nodirabegim Sadir qizi</i>	
Физическое воспитание студенческой молодежи в современных условиях	53
<i>Тангриев Абдукарим Товошович</i>	
Tibbiyot instituti talabalarida professional tibbiy muloqot ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	57
<i>Umarkulov Mukhtorali Islomkulovich</i>	
Orqa miya shikastlanishida adaptiv jismoniy tarbiya vositalaridan foydalanish.....	60
<i>Xalilova Barnogul Abdulazizovna, Shaxbazova Gulrux Orifjon qizi</i>	
Творчества Скотта Туроу в оценке литературной критики	64
<i>Хайдарова Умида Пулатовна</i>	
Sport kurashi usullarini tasnifi, tizimi va ularning atamasi	69
<i>A. R. Xodjanov</i>	
Роль образования в реабилитации и реинтеграции детей-репатриантов	73
<i>Юлдашев Санжар Рuzимуродович</i>	
O'quvchilarda liderlik xislatlarini shakllanishining gender jihatlarini.....	78
<i>Yuldasheva Sevara Ruzimurodovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni partisipativ tayyorlashda ijtimoiy-perseptiv ko'nikmalarning ahamiyati	81
<i>Muradova Maftuna Komilovna</i>	
Sport kurashi usullarining tasnifi, tizimi va ularning atamasi	84
<i>Faxriddin Karimov</i>	
Yuqori sinflarda ingliz tili darslarida grammatik interferensiyani aniqlash va uni bartaraf etish usullari.....	88
<i>Amirqulova Dilnoza Bahriddin qizi</i>	
Pedagogik ta'lim innovatsion klasteri yondashuvi asosida bo'lajak mutaxassislarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	91
<i>Baybayeva Muxayyo Xudaybergenovna, Zulxaydarov Javlonbek Abdukaxor o'g'li</i>	
The Role of Non-Governmental Higher Education Institutions in Contemporary Educational Systems and their Economic Impact.....	94
<i>I. Imomov</i>	

Ingliz tilini o'rganishda autentik materiallardan foydalanish metodikasini takomillashtirish modeli	100
<i>Ismatova Madina Inomjon qizi</i>	
Elektron darsliklardan samarali foydalanish uchun qo'yilgan talablarning asosiy mezonlari.....	103
<i>Jumanov Xudoyor Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
Xorijiy tajribalar asosida ta'lim sifatini boshqarishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	106
<i>Karimova Maxbuba Mukimjonovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim talabalarida "health care" tafakkurini shakllantirishning pedagogik zaruriyati.....	109
<i>Mattiyev Ilhom Begmatdulobovich</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarining boshqaruvida jamoa motivatsiyasini oshirishdagi rahbarning roli.....	113
<i>Mirzayeva Faroxat Odiljonovna, Shukurova Shaxzodaxon Xolbek qizi</i>	
Yangi o'zbekiston taraqqiyot davrida tarbiyaviy texnologiyalar asosida yuksak ma'naviyatli shaxsni shakllantirish.....	116
<i>Nigmanova Umidaxon Baxodirxon qizi, Quvondiqova Dildora Komiljonovna</i>	
Oilaviy va axloqiy qadriyatlarni tarbiyalashda oila va maktab hamkorligi – pedagogik muammo	121
<i>Saidova Barno Narzullayevna</i>	
Talaba-yoshlarda reproduktiv salomatlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari va imkoniyatlari..	125
<i>Shodmonova Shoira Saidovna, Shodmonova Dilsora Shokirovna</i>	
Futbol ko'nikmalarini etnosport elementlari asosida shakllantirish.....	129
<i>Toshpo'latov Sirojjon Komiljon o'g'li</i>	
Abdulla Avloniy pedagogik merosida yoshlar ekologik tafakkurini rivojlantirish g'oyalari	132
<i>Umarova Malika Xisabidinovna</i>	
Umumta'lim muassasalarida – ta'lim sifatini boshqarish ustuvor yo'nalish sifatida	137
<i>Yakubova Muxtaram Abdumavlyanovna</i>	
Использование современных педагогических технологий на занятиях иностранного языка	140
<i>Виктория Мамаджанова</i>	
Открытое занятие физкультурный досуг "Колобок"	144
<i>Кинжабаева Дильбар Абдурафиковна</i>	
Толерантность у учителей: значение, роль и пути формирования.....	147
<i>Уразова М.Б., Бекбосынова З.К.</i>	
Ingliz tilini o'qitishda o'qish ko'nikmasini o'rgatishning an'anaviy va zamonaviy turlari talqini.....	153
<i>O'rinova Durdona Farhodovna</i>	
Deontologik yondashuv asosida maktab boshqaruvining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	156
<i>Abdulxayeva Moxiraxon Borixonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni milliy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiyalashning ahamiyati	160
<i>Ataniyazova O'g'iljan Rajapbayevna</i>	
O'quvchilarning neyropedagogik xususiyatlarini diagnostika qilish	163
<i>Babakulova Dilnoza Ramazonovna</i>	
Kasbiy ijtimoiylashuv – bo'lajak o'qituvchi huquqiy ijtimoiylashtirishning asosiy omili sifatida	167
<i>Ibotov Javohir Ulug'bekovich</i>	
Maktab direktorining boshqaruv faoliyatida qarorlarni qabul qilishda tavakkalchilikni boshqarish	170
<i>Jabborova Yulduzxon Hasan qizi</i>	
10-11-sinf o'quvchilarining biologiya fanini o'rganishda innovatsion fikrlash ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishning amaldagi holati.....	173
<i>Sharipova Aziza Mustafayevna</i>	
Bolalardagi inqiroz va uning sabablari.....	176
<i>Xasanova Iroda Alimjonovna</i>	
O'zbek adabiyotida modernizm va postmodernizm unsurlari	181
<i>Yuldasheva Dilnoza Bekmurodovna</i>	
"Taym menejment" ko'nikmalari asosida o'quvchilar vaqtini samarali boshqarish imkoniyatlarini shakllantirish	184
<i>Yuldasheva X.Q.</i>	

Динамика психологического благополучия личности студентов-психологов.....	191
<i>Тиллашайхова Хосият Азаматовна</i>	
Markaziy Osiyo tilshunosligining rivojlanish bosqichlari	194
<i>Abdimo'minova Dildora Oybekovna</i>	
Autizm spektrida buzilish aniqlangan bolalar ta'lim-tarbiyasida ota-onalarning roli.....	198
<i>Alimova Gulchehra Qobilovna</i>	
Autizm spektrida buzilish aniqlangan bolalarning ijtimoiy hayotdagi o'rni	201
<i>Asrarxanova E'tibor Abduvaxob qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kasbiy mahoratni shakllantirish texnologiyasi	206
<i>G'iyasova Nargiza Yunus qizi</i>	
Is'hoqxon to'ra ibrat asarlari asosida talabalarni pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash	210
<i>Mirzayeva Faroxat Odiljonovna, Jo'rayeva Sitora Eshqobil qizi</i>	
Pedagogik dasturiy vositalarni yaratishda ranglar tizimidan foydalanish	214
<i>Mamanazarov Baxrom Jumonovich</i>	
Solving Specific Problems With Specific Methodological Approaches	218
<i>Muxammedova Nafisa Kamolovna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining raqamli kompetentligini oshirish masalalari va ularning yechimlari	223
<i>Raxmatova Hamida Ismatillo qizi</i>	
Integratsiyalashgan musiqa mashg'ulotlari jarayonida musiqiy idrokni shakllantirishga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim metodlari.....	227
<i>Ruziyeva Orzigul Ilyosovna</i>	
XXI asrda tasavvufning ma'naviy-tarbiyaviy jihatlari.....	230
<i>Quvonov Sardor Zokirovich</i>	
Mirzo Ulug'bekning pedagogik g'oyalari va uning ta'lim rivojidagi xizmatlari.....	233
<i>Soatova Rayxona Sadridin qizi</i>	
Yashil iqtisodiyotning ta'lim sifatiga ijobiy ta'sirlari	236
<i>To'rabekov Farxod Sanakulovich</i>	
Umumta'lim maktabi 5-6-sinf o'qituvchilarini jismoniy tarbiyaga o'qitishda ilmiy-pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish nazariy asoslari	240
<i>Toshtemirov Bekzod Faxriddin o'g'li</i>	
Tarbiya nazariyasiga doir ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar va raqamli dunyoda tarbiya masalalarining nazariy-metodik asoslari.....	244
<i>Yusupova Mahliyo Abdimo'min qizi</i>	
Использование современных педагогических технологий на занятиях иностранного языка	248
<i>Виктория Мамаджанова</i>	
Использование аутентичных материалов в преподавании русского языка: преимущества и недостатки	252
<i>Умаров Азиз Авазович</i>	
O'qituvchilarda kasbiy identifikatsiyani rivojlantirish: tamoyillar, yondashuvlar va amaliy tajribalar.....	256
<i>Abdusamiyev Dilmurod Abdug'ani o'g'li</i>	
Kasbiy-pedagogik kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari	260
<i>Abrorxonova Kamolaxon Abrorxon qizi</i>	
Basketbolchilar uchun reabilitatsiya usullari va jarohatlarning oldini olish strategiyalari	263
<i>Suyunov Tohir Nomoz o'g'li</i>	
Yosh dzyudochilarni tayyorlashda innovatsion usullar: pedagogik va psixologik yondashuvlar.....	267
<i>Husanov G'aybulla Usmanovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim sohasida pedagog olimlarning milliy qadriyatlar asosida ekologik tarbiya berishga oid qarashlari.....	271
<i>Ergasheva Umrinisso Komilovna</i>	
Nurota tog' tizmasining tabiiy geografik xususiyatlari.....	275
<i>Esonqulova Dilbar Sayitovna</i>	

Teacher's motivational management strategies for innovative activities	279
Egamberdiev Farkhod Botirovich	
Futboldagi psixologik trening: stressga bardoshlilikni oshirish usullari.....	283
Davronov Ernazar Orziyevich	
Yosh o'qituvchilar faoliyatida pedagogik qiyinchiliklar va ularni bartaraf etishning psixologik asoslari.....	287
Jumanova Nasiba Sherbojevna	
Tarbiyasi og'ir bolalarni ijtimoiylashtirishda oila, mahalla va maktab hamkorligi ishlari samaradorligining mazmuni.....	290
Kamolova Shirinoy Usarovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish savodxonligi darslarida sharq mutafakkirlarining ma'naviy merosidan foydalanishning samaradorligi	294
Maxmudova Muhlisa Abdilaziz qizi	
Ta'lim boshqaruvida maktab ta'limi tizimi statistikasini shakllantirish zaruriyati.....	297
Muradov Ikrom Turdiboyevich	
Using Movement Games in Teaching English in Preschools	301
Nishonova Ra'nokhon Abdullojon qizi	
The Role and Opportunities of Using Modern Methods in Improving Geographic Knowledge Among School Students.....	304
Ortiqova Iqbol Olimboyevna	
O'quvchilarni kasb-hunarga yo'naltirishda sharq allomalarining ma'naviy merosidan foydalanishning psixologik asoslari	310
Qarshiboeva Dilfuza Burliyevna	
O'quv faoliyati samaradorligiga ta'sir qiluvchi emotsional intellektni rivojlantirishning psixologik asoslari	314
Sangirova Nilufar	
Futbolda texnik va taktik tayyorgarlikning yosh futbolchilar rivojlanishiga ta'siri.....	317
Sultonov Vaxob Murotovich	
Ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishda ota-onalar bilan muloqot imkoniyatlaridan foydalanishning ilmiy asoslari.....	321
Toshpo'latova Nodira Xudjamurodovna	
O'smirlarda kuzatiladigan serzardalikning kelib chiqishi va korreksiyasi.....	325
Tuxtayeva Maxliyo Shamsiddinovna	
Yosh voleybolchilar uchun psixologik tayyorgarlikning o'yin samaradorligiga ta'siri.....	329
Suyunov Tohir Nomoz o'g'li	
Leveraging Global Economic Trends to Enhance English Language Education: A Methodological Approach for Economics Students	333
Z. Xasanova	
Некоторые семантические характеристики французских и узбекских антропонимов	336
Камолова Санобар Джаббаровна	
Стратегии подготовки специалистов для инклюзивного образования в Республике Казахстан (Опыт КазНУ)	340
Магайова А. С.	
Проектирование современной образовательной среды школы на основе художественного метода .	346
Рузметова Хилола Абдушориповна	
Inklyuziv ta'lim jarayonidagi boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini kollaborativ yondashuv asosida milliy tarbiyalashning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari.....	352
Ergashev Jahongir Mamanazarovich	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning deontologik xususiyatlarini shakllantirishning psixologik asoslari	357
Ahmedova Nasiba Achilovna	
Ilk bolalik davrining psixologik xususiyatlari.....	361
Askarova Nafisa Avazovna	
Oila – yoshlarni chet tillarni o'rganish jarayoniga ta'sir etuvchi ijtimoiy institut sifatida.....	365
Atamuxamedova Ra'no Fazildjanovna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Ilon obrazi qadimgi sharq xalqlari moddiy madaniyatida aks etishi 368 <i>Choriyeva Sedona Sharif qizi</i>
	Organization of Sports and Wellness Activities in Higher Educational Institutions 373 <i>Dehkonova Mahmuda Ortigovna</i>
	Xorijiy tajribalar asosida tarbiya jarayoni samaradorligini oshirish 376 <i>Farsaxonova Dilafruz Rizaxonovna</i>
	O'zbekistondagi kichik biznes subyektlarini banklar orqali moliyaviy rag'batlantirishning samaradorligini tahlil qilish va baholash 379 <i>Hamroqulov Xushbaxt Sadriddinovich</i>
	"Forsayt" texnologiyalari tarixi va undan sport ta'limida foydalanish imkoniyatlari 382 <i>Hayitov Oybek Eshboyevich</i>
	Fitonimlarning etimologik va leksik-semantik xususiyatlari (fransuz va o'zbek tillari misolida)..... 386 <i>Jumashova Sayyora Shonazarovna</i>
	Harakatli o'yinlarning tarixi, turkumlari va pedagogik ahamiyati 390 <i>Kulboyev Nodirjon Salaydinovich</i>
	Texnologiya darslarida STEAM ta'lim yondashuvi asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kreativlik qobiliyatini rivojlantirish 393 <i>Kulboyeva Dilnoza Abdug'ofurovna</i>
	O'smirlarda agressiv xulq-atvorning namoyon bo'lishi va uni bartaraf etish mexanizmlari..... 396 <i>M. S. Usmonova</i>
	Bo'lajak pedagoglarda STEAM ta'limini joriy etishning nazariy asoslari va ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyati..... 400 <i>Nurullayeva Ugulxon Ergashboyevna</i>
	Kurashchilarning musobaqa oldi texnik-taktik tayyorgarligi 405 <i>Ochilov Elbek Olimovich</i>
	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti metodistining murakkab va ko'p qirrali bo'lgan vazifalari 408 <i>Otaxanova Manzura G'ofurovna, Jo'rayeva Saida</i>
	Kognitiv pedagogika – o'quvchilarning aqliy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish omili 412 <i>Qabulov Baxrom Quzibayevich</i>
	Badiiy matnda o'ziniki bo'lmagan ko'chirma gaplarning uslubiy vazifalari..... 418 <i>Siddiqova Shoxida Isoqovna</i>
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarining badiiy va obrazli iste'dodini media ta'lim orqali rivojlantirish..... 422 <i>Xalillayeva Go'zaloy Mo'minjon qizi</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini ijodiy faoliyatga tayyorlash texnologiyasini tashkil etishning pedagogik asoslari 426 <i>Yusupova Sanobar Odil qizi</i>
	O'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlashini shakllantirish maqsadida masalalar sistemasini tanlash texnologiyalari 431 <i>Zokirov Furqat Muxsinovich</i>
	Эффективность использования ИКТ в контроле учебных достижений в старших классах образовательной школы 437 <i>Уразова М. Б., Асанова К. У.</i>
	Проблемы преподавания русского языка в вузах Узбекистана 441 <i>Норбоева Дилафруза Джумакуловна</i>
	Социальные особенности семей, воспитывающих детей с интеллектуальными нарушениями 444 <i>Пирманова Бахора Эшмухаммедовна</i>
	Geymifikatsiyadan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilar motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati 449 <i>Xaitova Nazokat</i>

ORGANIZATION OF SPORTS AND WELLNESS ACTIVITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: An important role in the upbringing of the younger generation as physically healthy individuals is played by the improvement of physical education, sports, and recreational activities in educational institutions. This article highlights physical education and sports in educational institutions, morning physical exercises, physical education classes, sports clubs, sports competitions and celebrations, as well as independent exercises and training using natural factors.

Key words: physical education, morning exercise, sports, independent practice, sports clubs, competitions.

Annotatsiya: Ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya va sport, sog'lomlashtirish tadbirlarini takomillashtirish yosh avlodni jismonan barkamol inson qilib tarbiyalashda katta ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqolada ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya va sport, sog'lomlashtirish tadbirlari, ertalabki badan tarbiya, jismoniy tarbiya darslari, sport to'garaklaridagi mashg'ulotlar, sport musobaqalari va bayramlari, shuningdek, jismoniy mashq bilan mustaqil shug'ullanish hamda tabiat omillari yordamida chiniqish masalalari yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Jismoniy tarbiya, badan tarbiya, sport, mustaqil shug'ullanish, sport to'garaklari, musobaqalar.

Аннотация: Важную роль в воспитании подрастающего поколения как физически здоровых людей играет совершенствование физического воспитания и спорта, а также оздоровительные мероприятия в учебных заведениях. В статье рассматриваются занятия физкультурой и спортом в образовательных учреждениях: утренняя физкультура, занятия физкультурой, спортивные секции, спортивные соревнования и праздники, а также самостоятельные упражнения и тренировки с использованием природных факторов.

Ключевые слова: физическое воспитание, утренняя физкультура, спорт, самостоятельная практика, спортивные секции, соревнования.

INTRODUCTION

In order to connect the youth of each region with bonds of friendship, cooperation, and mutual solidarity in the upbringing of physically healthy and mentally mature youth in our country, three-stage sports competitions and celebrations have been organized. Competitions among schoolchildren, "Umid Nihollari," sports competitions among students of professional colleges, "Barkamol Avlod" sports games, and sports competitions, "Universiade," among students of higher educational institutions are regularly organized and held in each region.

At the heart of these competitions lies the development of students' physical fitness, their ability to work and defend, and, most importantly, the targeted use of physical culture and sports in forming healthy lifestyle skills.

To ensure the continuity of the process of health and physical development of students, physical education activities are identified and implemented as part of the agenda for schoolchildren and students. ^[1]

LITERATURE REVIEW

The content of the agenda is based on the Physical Education Program. In the organization of physical education events, the physical culture team manages the organizational and leadership roles. The agenda of physical education aims to strengthen the mental abilities of students and pupils, contribute to their physical development, improve their health, and enhance discipline. Regular physical education teaches students self-control, adherence to the agenda, and strengthens their activity. Physical education activities are a form

of educational and pedagogical work of educational institutions and should be organized in accordance with training sessions.

In the process of physical education, teachers address the tasks of the educational stages using teaching methods to teach students movements and help them master exercise techniques. The process of teaching physical education in educational institutions depends on the correct organization of the principles and methods of education. [2]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The process of education in physical education addresses the task of equipping pupils and students with specialized knowledge of physical culture and sports, as well as developing techniques and skills in exercise and movement. In physical education, it is observed that the repetition and reinforcement of exercises multiple times, based on different requirements, ensures smooth execution of exercise techniques. This, in turn, enhances movement skills and abilities. Basics of physical and sports training. [3]

Different types of training in physical education and sports include technical, tactical, theoretical, mental-voluntary, and physical training. Physical training focuses on general and specific physical qualities such as strength, speed, endurance, agility, and flexibility, which naturally evolve with age. Emphasis is placed on the legitimacy of using basic tools and plans for physical development. [4]

Mass sports and high-performance sports have distinct purposes and missions. The structure of the entire process of sports training and its components is considered, along with the fundamentals of sports training methods. [5]

Sports Training Planning and Organizational Activities

Exercise is the foundation of the integrity of the training structure. Morning exercise. Morning gymnastics, a daily activity conducted before classes, addresses educational and well-being objectives. Outdoor exercises also contribute to strengthening the bodies of pupils and students. Morning physical education classes instill discipline in students, ensuring an organized start to the training day. [6]

In morning physical education classes, students perform exercises that enhance their daily lives, learned during physical education lessons. Participation is open to all students unless medically restricted. [6]

The morning physical education classes are supervised by the director and deputy director of academic affairs, with sessions conducted by physical education teachers. Members of the youth association and active student-athletes also assist in organizing these sessions.

As many pupils and students as possible should be involved in physical training and sports clubs, including children with slight physical developmental delays. [7]

Leaders of sports clubs should possess expertise in training methodologies for specific sports and understand the nuances of working with students. Physical development, physical fitness, age, and gender differences are considered when involving pupils and students in physical training and sports clubs within specialized sports institutions. [8]

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

With the correct organization and management of sports, it is possible to achieve positive results in the development of the body and the demonstration of sports achievements in various disciplines. General physical training clubs promote the physical development of pupils and students. Club activities can be planned throughout the year as follows: in autumn – movement and sports games, athletics; in winter – winter sports, gymnastics, wrestling; in spring – cross-country training, sports games; and in summer – swimming lessons. General physical education classes are organized on the basis of physical education principles. The general physical fitness of pupils and students is monitored during competitions and sports holidays. Club members usually consist of 15 to 20 people. The groups are selected from students of the same age, gender, and physical fitness. Classes are held once or twice a week, and each session lasts around 60 minutes.

Physical training group leaders are assigned to their groups and assist the coaches. Sports clubs in educational institutions also attract students based on their physical fitness, personal interests, and abilities. These sports clubs operate in accordance with a physical education program. Athlete students' physical fitness is monitored during group classes, sports competitions, and holidays. Classes are organized 3–4 times a week for 60–90 minutes. The availability of necessary equipment, specialist trainers, and proper training facilities ensures the preparation of qualified athletes.

Excursions, walks, and tourist tours have great educational and developmental value. During these activities, pupils and students get acquainted with nature, their homeland, and its attractions. These activities help to improve skills such as walking, running, and playing, strengthen the body, and enhance health. They also contribute to the development of abilities such as planning, self-service, standing, and walking. Such activities

play an invaluable role in decision-making, team-building, and fostering friendship and camaraderie. Through these experiences, students can benefit from the healing properties of nature, such as sunlight, water, and fresh air, while gaining an understanding of the natural and historical landmarks of their country.

During hikes, pupils and students perform essential physical activities such as walking, running, jumping, climbing, swimming, and bathing, using natural resources. They are provided with the necessary equipment for hiking to ensure safety and comfort.

Sports competitions are one of the most engaging forms of extracurricular physical education in educational institutions. They help pupils and students engage in regular physical activities both at home and in physical culture communities, enhancing their physical fitness and overall health. Competitions, along with other extracurricular activities, are included in the general annual work plan of the educational institution. At the beginning of the academic year, the terms, rules, and programs for competitions are clearly defined. Preparations for the competitions are made in advance according to these deadlines.

Each competition is conducted according to a specific charter, which outlines the goals and objectives of the competition, time and location, participants, program, conditions, registration process, award procedures, and application deadlines. Sports holidays can also be dedicated to celebrations or national events. These events involve athlete performances, opening ceremonies, flag-raising, national and youth anthem performances, public exercises and activities, entertainment, and awarding prizes to winning individuals or teams. The closing ceremony of such events is conducted solemnly, and participants are provided with incentives and benefits in preparation for future events.

Pupils and students are also encouraged to participate in independent physical education and sports activities during their free time. These activities are conducted in the form of independent exercises once the necessary skills and abilities have been developed. The content of independent physical education includes general physical training exercises, developmental exercises, physical quality improvement, and exercises with equipment, as well as sports and action games. Walking in nature, bathing, and sunbathing can also be organized as part of independent classes.

Exercises are categorized into related groups and distributed according to their effects and properties. The selection of exercises is based on the development level of physical qualities and motor skills. These exercises are applied in various areas, including physical education theory and methodology, exercise biomechanics, and sports physiology.

CONCLUSION

The processes of physical development of pupils and students in physical education and sports activities are organized through the performance of physical activities and exercises. Positive changes in physical development are reflected in the body structure of children, including height gain, weight gain, and an increase in chest circumference due to the expansion of lung vital capacity. These changes also involve an increase in muscle strength, improvements in muscle shape, and enhanced resistance of the cardiovascular system and other organs to physical loads. These developments are continuously monitored and evaluated.

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